

Navigating Ethical Considerations in Participatory Research: Key Challenges and Insights

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A medicalised perception of Autism as a neurodevelopmental disorder has been prevalent in Autism research, however, in recent decades, there has been a growing shift toward the neurodiversity paradigm within Autism research, with a focus on differences in strengths and abilities rather than deficits. A substantial amount of research has focused on student well-being, however, there is a paucity of studies eliciting the views and perspectives of Autistic young people specifically, how they conceptualise well-being and what could promote or enhance their well-being. The existing literature on Autistic young people's well-being often positions them as subjects rather than active contributors. Every young person has the right to share their views on issues that impact their lives and should not face discrimination based on disability. Therefore, it is paramount that we as researchers uphold young people's ethical right to contribute to this decision-making process in providing support and guidance to all young people to express their views as part of a young person's rights-based perspective. Considering these gaps, this paper aims to explore the ethical considerations involved in designing a participatory consultation with Autistic young people about well-being through the formation of Young People's Research Advisory Groups (YPRAGs).

Keywords: Autism; Neurodiversity Paradigm; Well-being; Participatory Methods; Ethical Considerations

Highlights

- This paper discusses the design of a neuro-affirming participatory study that meaningfully includes Autistic young people. Following a meta-synthesis of existing literature relating to Autistic young people's conceptualisations of well-being, Autistic young people will be consulted with to explore and understand their perspectives on how Autistic well-being is conceptualised and constructed within the literature.
- This paper discusses unique ethical considerations and methodological insights prior to consultations with Autistic young people to ensure their voices are respected and valued.
- This paper contributes to the growing body of work advocating for the use of neuro-affirming participatory approaches to ensure that Autistic young people's perspectives are truly heard, valued and prioritised. This research will support a growing plan for future research in direct consultation with Autistic young people and will also provide a valuable insight into how best to facilitate this process in future research.

Funding Statement: This work is supported by the Dublin City University Educational Trust PhD Scholarship in Autism Education, awarded to Laura McGrath.

Introduction

Autism is a neurodevelopmental condition, characterised by a diverse spectrum of attributes in social communication and interaction, and often repetitive patterns of behaviours and interests (American Psychiatric Association (APA), 2013). The conventional medical paradigm views Autism as a disability which arises from an individual's biological structure and function (Pellicano and den Houting, 2022). This medicalised perception of Autism as a neurodevelopmental disorder has been at the forefront of Autism research. However, in recent decades, including Autistic people in shaping research that impacts them aligns with the principles of the neurodiversity movement, which focuses on strengths and abilities as opposed to deficits (Pellicano and den Houting, 2022). As suggested by Humphrey and Parkinson (2006), Autistic voice can be largely underrepresented, as research tends to be conducted *on them* rather than *with them*. However, there have been efforts to promote the meaningful inclusion of Autistic voices in research (Milton, Mills and Pellicano, 2014; Lundy, 2007). For example, the Lundy Model (2007) embeds participation within a rights-based ethical framework and emphasises that participation is not just solely about hearing voices but ensuring that these voices are truly valued and can influence research and/or practice. Although participatory approaches have been widely accepted as an inclusive and effective method for conducting research with Autistic people (Den Houting et al., 2021), there remains ethical and methodological challenges when utilising participatory approaches with Autistic young people, particularly when exploring sensitive topics such as well-being. These challenges include, securing meaningful consent/assent, risks and safeguarding, ensuring privacy and confidentiality and flexibility in design.

Although a substantial body of research on well-being exists, there remains a paucity of studies exploring the well-being of Autistic young people specifically and what positively contributes to the well-being of Autistic individuals (Najeeb and Quadt, 2024). This paper explores important insights and challenges in designing a participatory research study about Autistic well-being grounded in a children's rights-based approach.

Research Aims

This study involves consultations with Autistic young people to elicit their views and perspectives on well-being based on the findings from a meta-synthesis exploring how Autistic well-being has been defined and conceptualised within existing literature. This will be addressed in two parts as outlined below:

Part One: Meta-synthesis of Literature

The objective of the meta-synthesis is to synthesise qualitative studies relating to the well-being of Autistic young people aged 10-19 years.

Part Two: Consultation with Young People's Research Advisory Groups (YPRAGs)

Although the meta-synthesis will provide important insight into the conceptualisation of Autistic well-being as evidenced in the literature, it is important to directly consult with Autistic young people as all young people have the right to express their views as outlined by the UNCRC (2005). The aim of the consultations is to explore and understand Autistic young people's perspectives on how Autistic well-being is conceptualised and constructed within the literature through the formation of a YPRAG. The remit of a YPRAG is to advise on the research process and provide insights and views on the topic being explored (Lundy et al., 2021). Based on the findings of the meta-synthesis, guidance will be sought from Autistic young people on ways to gather their views and perspectives on Autistic well-being.

Research Questions

This two-part qualitative study aims to answer the following research questions:

Meta-synthesis

1. How has well-being for Autistic young people been defined?
2. How do Autistic young people describe their well-being?
3. What methods are employed to gather Autistic young people's perspectives on well-being?

Consultations with Young People's Research Advisory Groups (YPRAGs)

1. To what extent do Autistic young people feel that the review findings align with their views and perspectives of Autistic well-being?
2. What are Autistic young people's perspectives on how best to consult with Autistic young people in relation to their well-being?
3. What are Autistic young people's key recommendations regarding the focus of future research consultations as part of this research (i.e. proposed demographic sample, language)?

Proposed Methods

The study will utilise qualitative participatory methods grounded in a children's rights-based approach (Lundy, 2007). The Lundy framework ensures that young people's voices are meaningfully heard and valued in line with the UNCRC (1989), whereby all children have the right to form and express their views on matters that affect them. The proposed methods for conducting this participatory research, developed through consultations with Autistic young people are outlined below.

Informed Consent and Assent

Prior to the YPRAG consultations, a plain language statement will be given to parents of participants and participants themselves. All details pertaining to the research will be included; the aim of the research, why the research is being conducted, benefits of taking part, how and where the research will be shared, what the study will involve, how the data will be protected and stored and any potential risks. An informed consent form will be provided for parents, and informed consent and assent forms for young people. It will be required by the researcher that another adult stays in the 'YPRAG' room to alert the researcher to any subtle forms of dysregulation of the young person and to support in case of decision to withdraw.

Participants and Sample Size

Participants will be young people with a diagnosis of Autism or who self-identify as Autistic. Participants must be aged between 10 and 19 years old. A maximum of two YPRAGs will be established (Lundy et al., 2021). One YPRAG will comprise of maximum 10 participants (aged 10-14) and the other YPRAG will comprise maximum of 10 participants (aged 15-19). These age ranges have been selected in response to Boshoff et. al's (2024) meta-synthesis findings and criteria. The sample size has been chosen to allow for possible attrition over the course of the study. Although engaging Autistic young people in research is highly rewarding, it can present challenges, such as, changes in interest over time and sensory sensitivities (Pellicano et al., 2014), this can contribute to higher-than-average attrition. This aligns with best practice guidelines whereby over-recruitment is recommended where attrition is likely (Shaw et al., 2019; Pickard et al., 2021).

Study Design

Following parent and young person consent/assent, two YPRAGs based on Lundy's (2007) participatory research model using focus group methodology will be established. Each participant

will engage in three YPRAG sessions. All sessions will take place over an 8-week period with each session lasting approximately 1 hour.

- Session 1 will involve ascertaining young people's assent alongside rapport building exercises (Lundy et al., 2011) and capacity building activities which are designed to familiarise the participants with issues around the topic of Autistic wellbeing in line with the Lundy (2007) model.
- Session 2 will examine the extent to which the review findings align with participants' views and perspectives. This will involve a range of participant led activities to elicit participant views on the review findings.
- Session 3 will gather participants' key recommendations for phase 2 of the research design and focus, to support future research consultations as part of this research.

All sessions and activities will be designed to be engaging and aligned with current best practice and research recommendations for working with Autistic young people (O'Keeffe and McNally, 2025; Lundy et al., 2011). Consideration will also be given to the participant communication preferences (verbal and non-verbal) to demonstrate their understanding and views (UN, 2009). YPRAGs will be semi-structured in nature and participants will have access to a range of tools to express views and will be prompted by the researcher with a series of short questions and photo prompts. Young people's responses across the YPRAG sessions will be analysed using reflexive thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2019).

Data Collection

All YPRAGs will be audio-recorded following parent/guardian consent and participant consent/assent. Audio will be recorded on a Dictaphone. Audio recordings will be transcribed manually by the researcher over a 2-week period after the YPRAG sessions have ended and the audio will be deleted from the DCU Google Drive immediately following the completion of transcriptions.

If a participant is using visual means of expressing views or responses to questions (through drawings, collages, note-taking, AAC devices, pictures), these will be captured using photography only with parental/young person consent and young person assent on a designated research tablet. These images will be directly uploaded to the researcher's DCU student Google Drive after each YPRAG session and then deleted from the research tablet immediately afterwards.

Ethical Considerations and Insights

The best interests of the young person in any research must be a primary consideration (UNCRC, 1989; O'Donnell, 2016). This approach leads to more meaningful insights that reflect the perspectives of Autistic young people. Consulting with Autistic young people in research involves unique ethical consideration, ensuring that their voices are respected and valued. Prior to consultations, ethical approval was granted from DCU's Research Ethics Committee. Four key ethical considerations in participatory research with Autistic young people are discussed below.

Informed Consent and Assent

Language in plain language statements must be adapted and tailored for parents and young people to meet varying communication needs. This ensures that young people get the necessary information to understand the decision, which is a core element of informed consent (Lundy, 2007).

In line with best practice principles for participation of disabled children (Kazmierczak-Murray, O'Mahony and Carey, 2024), a clear method for communicating assent will be established for each young person in advance of the YPRAG sessions. It is vital that a diverse range of accessible and creative communicative methods are used when obtaining consent and assent (O'Keeffe and McNally, 2025). Multiple versions of consent and assent forms will be designed, incorporating accessible language, visual supports and an interactive booklet available to both parents and participants online. Although assent will be sought from participants at the beginning of the sessions, assent is ongoing, and the researcher and assistant facilitator will remain attuned to verbal and non-verbal indicators of both assent and dissent throughout the process (Bourke and Loveridge, 2013). This is in line with the Lundy model as it supports understanding, respects young person's autonomy, and encourages genuine participation.

Risks and Safeguarding

The importance of carefully assessing risks and implementing robust safeguarding measures is critical when conducting studies involving consultations with young people. This will ensure their safety, respect their rights and support a comfortable and supportive research environment. A protocol and step-by-step guide have been designed in line with guidelines from Tusla (2025) in the event of a disclosure from a participant, and/or if a participant becomes upset, dysregulated or wishes to withdraw from the study. As emphasised in the Lundy model, this reinforces the importance of a holistic approach, values young people's voices and integrates their views in safeguarding practices.

Flexibility in Research Design

To foster equal participation, it is essential to use inclusive, accessible communication methods, such as visual supports, accessible language and Augmentative Communication Devices, to ensure young people are provided with equal opportunity to fully engage. Adopting a range of creative methods and multiple ways for young people to express their views is integral throughout the process (O’Keeffe and McNally, 2025; Lundy et al., 2011). According to the Lundy Model, creating a comfortable, safe and welcoming environment for Autistic young people throughout the YRPAG sessions is essential and ensures a young person’s participation rights as outlined in Article 12 of the UNCRC (Lundy, 2011). This will foster trust, encourage open and meaningful participation and help participants to feel respected and understood.

Privacy and Confidentiality

Ensuring participant anonymity is vital to prevent identification of participants. When using pseudonyms, it is important to clearly identify in plain language statements and consent and assent forms, how long the pseudonymised (alias name) data will be retained and the point at which any personal information relating to the participants will be deleted, the pseudonymised transcripts will then become anonymous. This information including timelines of data destruction and storage will be explained clearly in the information sheets and the consent and assent forms in an accessible way. This ensures that young people are respected as rights-holders and active agents in their own lives as described in the Lundy model (Lundy, 2007).

Limitations

As the consultation phase has not yet been completed, this paper discusses anticipated ethical challenges which may not entirely reflect the complexities that may arise in practice. To ensure meaningful participation, a variety of strategies as highlighted throughout this paper, have been embedded in the design of the consultations, to foster an inclusive and ethical process. Much of the literature highlights the potential power imbalance between adults and young people when conducting research *with* them (Alderson, 2008). However, following recommendations from previous research, this study adopts a rights-based approach to address this power differential, recognising the young person as a rights-holder and ensuring that their views will be taken seriously and respected (Lundy, 2007).

Finally, as highlighted by McKinney et al. (2021), non-speaking or minimally speaking Autistic individuals are often excluded from research. The consultation materials for this study have been designed to be accessible and flexible to meet the varying needs of participants.

Although this may not eliminate all limitations, they aim to foster meaningful participation in ethically grounded consultations.

Conclusions

This paper outlines the development of a neuro-affirming participatory study designed to meaningfully include Autistic young people in shaping understandings of Autistic well-being. Key ethical considerations and methodological approaches needed to create an inclusive and respectful environment are discussed. Centring the voices of Autistic young people contributes to the growing movement towards neuro-affirming participatory research.

There are ethical complexities when conducting participatory research with Autistic young people, but by creating safe and supportive environments and valuing their voice, we are ensuring that research is not only on them but more importantly, with them. When ethical principles are prioritised, we uphold our responsibilities as researchers while ensuring that every voice is genuinely heard, and that these voices can influence future research and practice.

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